

An integrated UAV system for wildfire evolution monitoring and data acquisition

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Abstract—Fighting wildfires is one of the most challenging and demanding tasks requiring quick response and precise coordination through effective decision-making. The continuous monitoring and estimation of wildfire propagation can provide time-critical information for better decision-making in compacting wildfires. In this paper, we propose an autonomous unmanned aircraft vehicle (UAV) system that is capable of monitoring the wildfire evolution but is also able to periodically fly ahead of the fire and collect valuable data (i.e., fuel data, weather data, etc.) that fire behavior analysts (FBAN) can use to anticipate better the fire behavior and movement. Specifically, we developed a control scheme that, based on a fire estimation model and an unscented Kalman filter (UKF), calculates target points and controls the UAV to monitor the fire. Moreover, the control scheme (based on the fire movement) periodically calculates virtual targets ahead of the fire and guides the UAV to visit for data acquisition. The proposed approach is evaluated in a simulation environment, demonstrating its effectiveness for fire monitoring and data acquisition.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wildfires are a real threat to natural ecosystems, wildlife, infrastructures, and human lives. They are also significant contributors to forest loss and a barrier to the fight against climate change [1]. According to the latest annual report from the European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS) [2], wildfires are a significant concern in the European Union since over 3400 km² of land were burned in 2020, with approximately 40% falling within the Natura2000 EU protected areas causing unparalleled damage. Even worst was the 2021 fire season, which is estimated to be the second-worst in the EU since 2017, with over 5000 km² of burned land and, unfortunately, many killed firefighters and civilians.

Fighting wildfires is a dangerous job that requires tremendous skills and precise timing to keep the fire under control. Key drivers for effectively compacting wildfires are early detection, continuous monitoring, and propagation estimation [3]. In fact, the more information is available in real-time for the fire evolution, the more effectively the mission commander can assess the situation and design a suitable plan to prevent the fire from spreading to new areas or evacuate people and properties before the fire arrives [4].

Common methods used for monitoring and tracking the fire evolution include the continuous inspection of satellite

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images and the use of manned aerial vehicles equipped with various sensors [5]. However, the constant improvement and extensive capabilities of unmanned aircraft vehicles (UAVs) have made them favorable for wildfire monitoring in recent years. Compared to common methods, the UAVs possess significant advantages for sensing and monitoring tasks since they conserve sizeable operation costs and minimize the risk compared to manned aerial vehicles. Furthermore, UAVs are available on-demand with various sensors onboard and can provide real-time coverage compared to the satellite coverage that is generally periodic with long revisit times.

UAVs received significant attention from the research community for tackling the wildfire monitoring task. A plethora of methods have been proposed and analyzed in review articles over the last few years [6]–[9]. The authors in [3] proposed a cooperative control method for monitoring the perimeter of a developing fire using a team of UAVs. The main objective of the approach is to guide the UAVs in clockwise and counterclockwise directions around the fire perimeter and meet at specific points, minimizing the information latency (i.e., state of fire perimeter) and the frequency of update to the mission base station. The fire perimeter tracking problem was also addressed in [10] with the authors proposing cooperative control for a team of UAVs based on optimization of utility functions keeping the UAVs close to the fire boundary.

The work in [5], recognizing the UAVs limited running time and payload capabilities, proposes pairing UAVs with unmanned ground vehicles (UGVs) for fire monitoring missions. The authors develop algorithms for moving UGVs to assigned areas where the transported UAVs are deployed to monitor the fire spread continuously based on an elliptical fire model. In [11], the authors develop an importance-based

Fig. 1. Proposed UAV system for wildfire monitoring and data acquisition.

coordination method for wildfire monitoring using multiple UAVs. Specifically, rather than monitoring the whole fire perimeter with the same frequency as in the previously discussed methods, the UAVs are controlled to visit the higher importance perimeter points more frequently based on their fire spread rate. Similarly, the work in [12] focuses on controlling a network of UAVs to monitor only the faster-moving segment of the fire frontier. To achieve this task, the authors design a sliding-mode control algorithm that moves the UAVs to the faster-moving region of the fire according to an optimization setup.

The authors in [4], [13], motivated by [14], proposed a distributed control framework that enables a team of UAVs to monitor a wildfire spreading collaboratively. Specifically, by minimizing the information loss from the UAVs cameras associated with quantified fire heat intensity levels, the UAVs can monitor the fire-front of the fire as it spreads while maintaining coverage of the whole wildfire. Moreover, the UAVs keep a safe distance to avoid collisions, but they are close enough to enable communication. Finally, the work in [15] proposes a distributed control framework for navigating a team of UAVs to monitor the wildfire spreading while at the same time considering the areas of firefighter activity. By utilizing an adaptive extended Kalman filter (AEKF), the authors generate a fire-front uncertainty map and human uncertainty map from the GPS signal received by the firefighters. Then by minimizing a dual-criteria objective function, they derive the positions that the UAV agents must navigate for effective fire monitoring and active firefighter sensing.

In comparison to the previous works, in this paper, we proposed an autonomous UAV system that monitors the wildfire evolution in real-time but is also able to scan the area ahead of the fire with a high probability of burning and collect valuable data in real-time from the spot (i.e., fuel data, weather data, fire behavior data, etc.), as illustrated in Fig. 1. These data are crucial for the fire behavior analysts (FBAN), allowing them to anticipate better the fire behavior and movement, which significantly impacts decision-making and fire suppression operations. To achieve the above task, we utilize an unscented Kalman filter (UKF) with a fire estimation model that enables the UAV to estimate/predict the fire-front locations and their respective uncertainty. A two-part controller is then designed to calculate target points for the UAV to visit to monitor the fire-fronts and minimize the total uncertainty. Moreover, virtual targets ahead of the fire are also calculated based on the fire movement so that the UAV can acquire data that FBAN can use to anticipate the fire behavior and movement better. Subsequently, a motion planning part based on the artificial potential field method is developed that guides the UAV from its current position to the target points to monitor the spreading fire, detect newly generated fire-fronts, and acquire data ahead of the fire.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II provides some preliminaries regarding the fire propagation model employed in this work. Section III describes the problem, while Section IV derives the proposed UAV

based method for wildfire evolution monitoring and data acquisition. Finally, Section V presents simulation results illustrating the effectiveness of the proposed method and Section VI provides some concluding remarks.

II. PRELIMINARIES

A. Fire Propagation Model

The FARSITE model [16] is considered one of the most accurate wildfire models and it is used by several agencies around the world. In this work we utilize a simplified version of the FARSITE model which describes mostly the fire front growth [4]. Specifically, in a 2D plane each fire-front propagates using the following equations:

$$q_j(t+1) = q_j(t) + \Delta t c(R, U) \begin{bmatrix} \sin \Theta \\ \cos \Theta \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where $q_j = [x_j^q, y_j^q]^T$ are the coordinates of j -th fire-front. Δt is the time step, and Θ is the azimuth angle of the wind direction and y -axis ($0 \leq \Theta < 2\pi$) increasing in clock-wise direction. Finally, $c(R, U)$ is calculated using:

$$c(R, U) = \frac{R - \frac{R}{\text{HB}}}{2}, \quad (2)$$

where R is the steady-state rate of fire spreading (m min^{-1}) and is associated with the fuel, $\text{HB} = \frac{\text{LB} + (\text{LB}^2 - 1)^{0.5}}{\text{LB} - (\text{LB}^2 - 1)^{0.5}}$ with $\text{LB} = 0.936e^{0.2566U} + 0.461e^{-0.1548U} - 0.397$ where U is the mid-flame wind speed (m s^{-1}).

Finally, to consider the increase of fire fronts, the model in (1) is initialized with $N_0 \geq 1$ fire fronts, and at each time-step, the number of fire fronts is increased using the following condition:

$$N(t+1) = \begin{cases} N(t) + d & \text{if } w > \bar{w} \\ N(t) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (3)$$

where d is the number of new fire fronts, while $w \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1)$ is random uniform variable and $\bar{w} \in [0, 1]$ is a selected fixed threshold. Thus, if $w > \bar{w}$ then d new fire-fronts will be generated in the next time-step starting from the coordinates of d randomly select existing fire fronts.

Fig. 2 presents fire evolution simulation results using the propagation model in (1) at different time steps. The initial source consists of $N_0 = 10$ fire-fronts around (100, 100), as shown in Fig. 2(a), and increased according to (3) with $d \sim \mathcal{U}(1, 3)$ and $\bar{w} = 0.01$. The simulation assumes that the wind flows northeast with a direction normally distributed $\Theta \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_\Theta = \frac{\pi}{4}, \sigma_\Theta = 3)$ and mid-flame wind speed half normally distributed $U \sim |\mathcal{N}(\mu_U = 6, \sigma_U = 2)|$. The steady-state rate of fire spreading R is pre-calculated for a discrete grid with 1×1 m cells following the half normal distribution $R \sim |\mathcal{N}(\mu_R = 5, \sigma_R = 2)|$, while $\Delta t = 1$ s.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

In this work, the problem we address is the real-time monitoring of a wildfire evolution and data acquisition ahead of the fire using a single autonomous flying agent or a UAV. We assume that the UAV agent is equipped with appropriate

Fig. 2. Simulation of wild fire evolution with fire-front increase at different time steps: (a) $t = 0s$, (b) $t = 1000s$, (c) $t = 2000s$, (d) $t = 3000s$.

devices for localization (i.e., GPS and IMU), a hyperspectral camera with proper software that enables fire detection, fire-front identification, and data acquisition for estimating the rate of spread, and sensors for measuring wind speed and angle. Moreover, we assume that the initial state of the fire is known, and the UAV is deployed by a depot at a safe distance from the fire.

By utilizing the UAV agent's sensing capabilities and agility, we would like to design a control scheme that guides the UAV to the most uncertain fire-fronts, allowing real-time monitoring of the wildfire evolution and providing accurate information regarding the state of the fire. Moreover, based on the fire movement, we would like the UAV to fly ahead of the fire and acquire data (i.e., fuel data, weather data, etc.) that help FBAN anticipate the fire propagation better. To design a control scheme for achieving the above tasks, we consider that the UAV agent:

- 1) Has a finite field of view (FOV), and its sensing capabilities depend on the flying altitude.
- 2) Can switch periodically from the fire monitoring task to the data acquisition task and take measurements from the area ahead of the fire at a predefined height.
- 3) Must maintain a safe predefined altitude to avoid getting caught in the fire, and also, it can fly up to a specified maximum altitude.

To address the problem, we first derive the UAV agent dynamics and its sensing model. A fire estimation model is also established to enable the UAV to estimate the fire-front locations and their respective uncertainty. Finally, we design a control scheme that allows the UAV to achieve the above objectives.

A. Agent Dynamics and Sensing Model

The UAV agent is free to fly in the 3D space and at a safe altitude from the fire. Let $p = [c, z]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$ denote the position of the UAV in the 3D space, in which $c = [x, y] \in \mathbb{R}^2$ denotes the 2D plane coordinates while $z \in \mathbb{R}$ denotes the altitude. The following discrete-time linear dynamical model gives the evolution of the UAV agent in the 3D space:

$$p(t+1) = p(t) + u(t)\Delta t, \quad (4)$$

where Δt denotes the time step and $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ denotes the control input. Specifically, the UAV is controlled by applying $u^s \in \mathbb{R}$ in each dimension, thus $u(t) = [u_x^s(t), u_y^s(t), u_z^s(t)]^T$ is the speed vector at time t .

The UAV must fly at a safe altitude to avoid getting caught in the fire and terminating its mission. Thus, it is critical to

Fig. 3. Illustration of the UAV agent square field of view (FOV), with total area $l \times l$ that depends on the UAV altitude z and the FOV opening angle φ .

keep the UAV above a minimum safety altitude from the ground. Moreover, according to the regulations, the UAV must also fly up to a maximum safe altitude. Assuming that the minimum safe altitude is z_{min} and the maximum safe altitude is z_{max} , then the UAV must always maintain the following condition:

$$z_{min} < \|p(t) - p^*(t)\| < z_{max}, \quad \forall t, \quad (5)$$

where $\|\cdot\|$ is the Euclidean distance, while $p^*(t) = [c(t), 0]^T$ is the projection for the UAV position to the ground.

The camera that enables fire detection and fire-front identification is attached at the bottom of the UAV and has a square field of view (FOV) as shown in Fig. 3, with side length l that is given by:

$$l(t) = 2z(t) \tan \frac{\varphi}{2}, \quad (6)$$

where $z(t) \in p(t)$ is the UAV altitude at t , and φ is the FOV opening angle (see Fig. 3) available from the camera specifications. Note that the camera is assumed to be mounted through a mechanism that enables it to be always perpendicular to the UAV body frame despite the roll/pitch rotations of the UAV during its motion. Lastly, the size of the FOV area is proportional to the flight altitude. Thus, lower altitude flights lead to a smaller FOV area with higher fidelity images and less noise, while higher altitude flights allow a larger FOV area with more image noise. This behavior is incorporated into the UAV sensing model by associating measurement noise with the flight altitude. In other words,

the measurements of fire fronts taken by the UAV include less noise in lower flight altitudes than in higher altitudes. Let γ be a zero-mean Gaussian noise with covariance matrix Γ , then the measurement noise v of the UAV sensing system is given by:

$$v(t) = \gamma(t) \frac{z(t)}{z_{min}}. \quad (7)$$

B. Fire Estimation

Using its sensing system, the UAV agent can detect the fire-fronts inside its FOV. However, for monitoring the fire that can cover a large area that cannot fit inside its FOV, the UAV employs an Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) to estimate the fire fronts locations. Then, the UAV can continuously monitor the active fire-fronts and detect new ones utilizing the control scheme described in the sequel. Thus, based on (1), the UAV uses the following model for the propagation of each fire front:

$$\begin{aligned} q_j(t+1) &= f(q_j(t), v(t)) + \omega(t) \\ q_{mj}(t) &= q_j(t) + v(t), \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $f(\cdot)$ denotes the fire model as described in (1), with $v(t) = [R, U, \Theta]$ representing the input values vector from the UAV onboard sensors, and q_{mj} denotes the measurement for the j -th fire front coordinates. Also, ω denotes the zero-mean Gaussian state noise with covariance matrix Q , while v is the measurement noise given in (7). Lastly, $q_j(0)$ is the initial position for the j -th fire front.

The UAV can estimate the location of each fire-front by utilizing UKF using (8) with the fire-front measurements $q_m(t)$ through the UAV's sensing system, and the input values $v(t) = [R, U, \Theta]$. In specific, at each time step, the UKF provides estimates for the location $\hat{q}_j \in \mathbb{R}^2$ of the j -th detected fire-front and its respective estimation error covariance $P_j = \rho_i^j \cdot I_2$, where $\rho_i^j \in \mathbb{R}$ are the P_j matrix components with $i = 1, 2$ and I_2 is the identity matrix of dimension 2×2 . The uncertainty of the j -th fire front at time step t , i.e., $\mathcal{H}_j(t)$, can be calculated using:

$$\mathcal{H}_j(t) = \text{Tr}(P_j(t)), \quad (9)$$

where $\text{Tr}(\cdot)$ is the trace operation on the error covariance $P_j(t)$ at time step t . Subsequently, the total uncertainty is calculated:

$$\mathcal{H}_{tot}(t) = \sum_{j=1}^{N_d(t)} \mathcal{H}_j(t) = \sum_{j=1}^{N_d(t)} \text{Tr}(P_j(t)), \quad (10)$$

where $N_d(t) \leq N(t)$ is the number of detected fire-fronts at time t .

IV. PROPOSED CONTROLLER

The proposed controller has two objectives. First, control the UAV agent to fly and take measurements from calculated target points that indicate highly uncertain fire-fronts to minimize the total uncertainty while maintaining safe altitude conditions. Second to periodically guide the UAV agent ahead of the fire into calculated virtual targets to acquire

Fig. 4. UAV agent controller architecture. The FM module uses UKF to estimate the fire-fronts location and their uncertainty and subsequently calculate the target points p_t . The DA module is activated periodically and calculates virtual target points p_{vt} that the UAV should visit for data acquisition. Based on the agent's current position, the MP module provides the necessary inputs to fly to the target points utilizing the artificial potential field method.

data (i.e., fuel data, weather data, etc.) that can be used by FBAN to anticipate the fire behavior and movement better. The proposed controller is depicted in Fig. 4 and consists of the Fire Monitoring (FM) module, the Data Acquisition (DA) module, and the Motion Planning (MP) module that we describe in the sequel.

A. Fire Monitoring

The FM module utilizes UKF as described in Section III-B to derive estimates for the location \hat{q} of the detected fire-fronts and their respective estimation error covariance P and subsequently the uncertainty of each fire-front as given in (9). Then, based on these estimates, the FM finds the target point that indicates the most uncertain fire-front location that the UAV must fly for measurements. Specifically, the 2D coordinates of the target point (tp), i.e., the coordinates of the most uncertain fire-front at each time-step t , can be derived using:

$$c_{tp}(t) = \hat{q}_n(t), \quad (11)$$

where the index n is given by:

$$n = \arg \max_{1 \leq j \leq N_d(t)} \mathcal{H}_j(t). \quad (12)$$

Additionally, the uncertain area of the targeted fire-front must fit into the UAV FOV for successful observation/measurement without the need for searching. This is achieved by associating the uncertainty of the targeted fire-front and the FOV's side length, as depicted in Fig. 5, to calculate the target altitude, i.e., z_{tp} . Specifically, using (6) the target altitude z_{tp} that the UAV must fly can be derived using:

$$z_{tp}(t) = \frac{2\sigma_{tp}(t)}{\tan \frac{\varphi}{2}}, \quad (13)$$

where $\sigma_{tb}(t)$ denotes the standard deviation of the targeted fire-front uncertainty given by:

$$\sigma_{tp}(t) = \sqrt{\arg \max_{\rho_i^n(t)} P_n(t)}, \quad (14)$$

Fig. 5. The target point p_{tp} is derived by finding the most uncertain fire-front estimate \hat{q}_j and its respective covariance P_j . The 2D plane coordinates of the target point c_{tp} are the estimated coordinates of that fire-front, while the target point altitude z_{tp} is adjusted so the uncertainty area of the target fire-front P_j fits to the FOV, i.e., $l = 4\sigma_{tp}$.

with $\rho_i^n(t) \in P_n(t)$ indicating the i -th element of covariance matrix $P_n(t)$ with the maximum value and index n as given in (12).

Specifically, and as shown in Fig. 5, $c_{tp}(t)$ holds the estimated coordinates of the most uncertain fire-front as given in (11), while $z_{tp}(t)$ is the altitude that the UAV needs to fly so that the uncertain area of the target fire-front fits to its FOV as given in (13). Thus, the 3D coordinates of the target point at each time step is:

$$p_{tp}(t) = [c_{tp}(t), z_{tp}(t)]. \quad (15)$$

If in the *Fire Monitoring* mode, the UAV must fly from its current position $p(t)$ to the target point $p_{tp}(t)$ and take measurements for minimizing the total uncertainty given in (10).

B. Data Acquisition

The DA module is activated periodically to calculate virtual target points ahead of the fire that the UAV must visit to acquire data that can help to anticipate the fire movement. To achieve this, first the current estimated fire-fronts $\hat{q}(t)$ are propagated Δt_{da} time steps ahead using (1) where Δt_{da} is set according to a selected lookahead horizon. Then the lookahead area set \mathcal{L} using set theory is calculated:

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{F}/\mathcal{C}, \quad (16)$$

where \mathcal{F} is the set of propagated fire-fronts and \mathcal{C} is the set of the fire perimeter area covered by the UAV. Subsequently, the virtual target points (i.e., the points for data acquisition) are calculated. Specifically, the 2D coordinates of the virtual target points are uniformly selected from the lookahead area

$$c_{vt} = \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{L}), \quad (17)$$

where the number of virtual target points n_{vt} is associated with the size of the lookahead area $n_{vt} = \text{Area}(\mathcal{L})m_{vt}$ where m_{vt} is a selected parameter. Finally, the height that the

UAV must fly to acquire data is pre-set to z_{vt} according to the onboard equipment specifications. Therefore, the virtual target points for data acquisition are given by

$$p_{vt}(t) = [c_{vt}(t), z_{vt}(t)], \quad (18)$$

which are then transferred to the MP module when the UAV goes into the *Data Acquisition* mode.

The UAV switching between Fire Monitoring (FM) mode and Data Acquisition (DA) mode is shown with the simplified FSM diagram in Fig. 6. Specifically, the switch from FM mode to DA mode occurs initially T_{S0} time steps after the UAV is deployed, and then every Δt_{da} time steps. The switch from DA mode to FM mode occurs when all the calculated virtual targets are visited, which is denoted with the $vt_visited$ event in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. UAV switch between Fire Monitoring (FM) mode and Data Acquisition (DA) mode.

C. Motion Planning

The movement of the UAV agent to the target points and virtual target points is handled by the MP module that utilizes the artificial potential field method [17]. Specifically, the MP module creates attractive force that controls the UAV to move to the next target point while at the same time it creates repulsive forces to keep safety altitude constraints. Based on the UAV mode, i.e., Fire Monitoring or Data Acquisition, the next target point $p_{NT}(t)$ is given by

$$p_{NT}(t) = \begin{cases} p_{tp}(t), & \text{if in Fire Monitoring mode} \\ p_{vt}(t), & \text{if in Data Acquisition mode.} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

To move the UAV to the next target point $p_{NT}(t)$ from its current position $p(t)$ we utilize a quadratic function of distance as a potential function and subsequently we take its negative gradient to derive its corresponding attractive force:

$$U_{att}(p(t)) = \frac{1}{2}k_a \|p_{NT}(t) - p(t)\|^2$$

$$u_{att}(t) = -\nabla U_{att}(p(t)) = k_a(p_{NT}(t) - p(t)), \quad (20)$$

where k_a is a positive scaling factor.

Next, to maintain the safety altitude condition given in (5), we utilize two repulsive functions, one for the minimum safety altitude z_{min} and one for the maximum altitude z_{max} . Specifically, for the minimum safety altitude z_{min} we utilize

the following repulsive potential function:

$$U_{rep1}(p(t)) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}k_r \left(\frac{1}{\|p^*(t) - p(t)\|^2} - \frac{1}{z_{min}} \right)^2, & \text{if } \|p^*(t) - p(t)\| < z_{min} \\ 0, & \text{if otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

where k_r is a positive scaling factor. The corresponding repulsive force from (21) is given by:

$$u_{rep1}(t) = -\nabla U_{rep1}(p(t)) = a_{r1}k_r \left(\frac{1}{\|p^*(t) - p(t)\|} - \frac{1}{z_{min}} \right) \frac{1}{\|p^*(t) - p(t)\|^3} (p^*(t) - p(t))$$

$$a_{r1} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \|p^*(t) - p(t)\| < z_{min} \\ 0, & \text{if otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

Similarly, the repulsive force for the maximum safety altitude is given by:

$$u_{rep2}(t) = a_{r2}k_r \left(\frac{1}{\|p^*(t) - p(t)\|} - \frac{1}{z_{max}} \right) \frac{1}{\|p^*(t) - p(t)\|^3} (p^*(t) - p(t))$$

$$a_{r2} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \|p^*(t) - p(t)\| > z_{max} \\ 0, & \text{if otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

By combining the attractive and repulsive forces derived in (20) and (22)-(23), respectively, the control law for the UAV agent movement is given by:

$$u(t) = u_{att}(t) + u_{rep1}(t) + u_{rep2}(t), \quad (24)$$

and is applied in (4) moving the UAV accordingly. An overview of the proposed control scheme is shown in Algorithm 1.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

We evaluated the proposed scheme by conducting various simulation experiments in the Matlab environment. For the fire propagation model we use the same parameter values as described in Section II-A. For the UAV agent we set the safe minimum and maximum altitude at $z_{min} = 30m$ and $z_{max} = 120m$, respectively. For the UAV sensing model the FOV opening angle was set at $\varphi = 60^\circ$, while the sensing measurement noise was set as zero mean Gaussian $\gamma \sim \mathcal{N}([0, 0]^T, \Gamma_2)$ where $\Gamma_2 = \text{diag}(\sigma_\Gamma^2, \sigma_\Gamma^2)$ with $\sigma_\Gamma^2 = 3$. Also, for the fire estimation model in (8), the process noise was set as zero mean Gaussian $\omega \sim \mathcal{N}([0, 0]^T, Q_2)$ where $Q_2 = \text{diag}(\sigma_Q^2, \sigma_Q^2)$ with $\sigma_Q^2 = 1$. For the DA module, we set the following default values: $\Delta t_{da} = 200s$, $m_{vt} = 0.0001$, $z_{vt} = 35m$, $T_{S0} = 100s$. Finally, for the MP module the potential field controller's scaling parameters were set as $k_a = 0.3$ and $k_r = 0.1$. In all the simulation results the initial fire consist of $N_0 = 10$ fire-fronts starting around (100, 100), while the UAV is deployed from a depot in a safe distance from the fire around (500, 500).

Algorithm 1 UAV Control Scheme for Wildfire Monitoring and Data Acquisition

- 1: **Input:** Initial fire front locations \mathbf{q}_0 . UAV real-time position $p(t)$. Measurements for the fire-fronts locations $q_{mj}(t)$, $j \in N$ under the FOV, and input values $v(t) = [R(t), U(t), \Theta(t)]$ for the fire.
 - 2: **Output:** The new UAV position $p(t+1)$
 - 3: **while** in Mission **do**
 - 4: Use UKF with (8) to derive estimations for the fire-fronts locations $\hat{q}_j(t)$, $j \in N$ and their respective error covariance $P_j(t)$
 - 5: **if** in Fire Monitoring mode **then**
 - 6: Calculate $c_{tp}(t)$ and $z_{tp}(t)$ using (11) and (13)
 - 7: $p_{NT}(t) \leftarrow p_{tp}(t)$
 - 8: **else if** in Data Acquisition mode **then**
 - 9: Propagate $\hat{q}(t)$ Δt_{da} time steps using (1)
 - 10: Calculate lookahead area set \mathcal{L} according to (16)
 - 11: Calculate virtual targets $p_{vt}(t)$ using (17)-(18)
 - 12: $p_{NT}(t) \leftarrow p_{vt}(t)$
 - 13: **end if**
 - 14: Calculate $u_{att}(t)$, $u_{rep1}(t)$ and $u_{rep2}(t)$ according to (20), (22) and (23)
 - 15: Compute $u(t)$ according to (24):
 $u(t) = u_{att}(t) + u_{rep1}(t) + u_{rep2}(t)$
 - 16: Update UAV position: $p(t+1) = p(t) + u(t)\Delta t$
 - 17: **end while**
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Fig. 7 shows simulations results of the UAV trajectory as it monitors the fire and visits the virtual target points for data acquisition at different time steps: (a) $t = 600s$, (b) $t = 1000s$ and (c) $t = 1600s$. The UAV at $t = 0s$ is deployed at (467, 562) and flies to the fire at the safe altitude $z_{min} = 30m$. Then it monitors the fire evolution as described in Section IV-A. Periodically it switches to the data acquisition mode and calculates virtual target points based on the fire movement as described in Section IV-B. As can be seen in Fig. 7, the UAV manages to successfully observe the area ahead of the fire at all times.

Fig. 8 compares the actual fire with the UAV estimated fire. Specifically, Fig. 8(a) illustrates the fire evolution after 3000s using the model as given in (1). Fig. 8(b) illustrates the fire evolution as estimated by the UAV utilizing the proposed approach. Finally, Figs. 8(c)-(d) present the root-mean-square (RMS) error in x and y coordinates between the actual fire and the estimated by the UAV. As can be observed, the error increases as the fire becomes larger over time. This is expected since the UAV needs to cover more distance to monitor existing and newly generated fire-fronts and visit virtual target points. Also, the spikes that can be seen in both Figs. 8(c)-(d) are directly related to the periods that the UAV switches to the DA mode and visits the virtual target points.

Next, we conduct Monte Carlo simulations to examine how data acquisition affects fire monitoring. Specifically, 1500 random simulations with 3000s duration each have been conducted, examining the average total uncertainty of

Fig. 7. Simulation results of 3D UAV trajectory as it monitors the fire and visits the virtual target points for data acquisition at three different time steps: (a) $t = 600s$, (b) $t = 1000s$, and (c) $t = 1600s$. For each time step the observed area by the UAV ahead of the fire is shown and also the 2D position of the calculated virtual target points.

Fig. 8. Comparison of actual and UAV estimated fire: (a) Actual fire evolution after 3000s, (b) Estimated fire by the UAV using the proposed method after 3000s, (c) Root-mean-square (RMS) error of x -coordinate between the actual and detected fire-fronts over time, (d) RMS error of y -coordinate between the actual and detected fire-fronts over time.

Fig. 9. Average total uncertainty of fire-fronts over time with minimum and maximum observed values: (a) without the Data Acquisition (DA) capability, (b) with DA and period $\Delta t_{da} = 100s$, (c) with DA and period $\Delta t_{da} = 200s$.

fire-fronts calculated as given in (10) over time along with the maximum and minimum bounds for three cases with the results available in Figs 9(a)-(c). Specifically, Fig. 9(a) presents the average total uncertainty for the case that the DA capability is inactive, i.e., the UAV is only monitoring the fire. Fig. 9(b) presents the average total uncertainty for

the case that the DA capability is active with propagation and period $\Delta t_{da} = 100s$. Lastly, Fig. 9(c) similarly presents the average total uncertainty for the case that the DA capability is active with propagation and period $\Delta t_{da} = 200s$. As can be observed, the average total uncertainty increases for larger Δt_{da} values. This is reasonable since the UAV for larger

Δt_{da} takes measurements from a larger area since more virtual target points are calculated and needs to fly more time away from the fire. Finally, it is good to note the wavy behavior of uncertainty in Fig. 9(b)-(c), which is directly related to Δt_{da} . In more detail, when the UAV flies ahead of the fire for data acquisition, the average total uncertainty increases, and when it returns to the fire, it decreases.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we proposed a control scheme that enables a UAV agent to monitor the wildfire evolution in real-time but also to fly ahead of the fire and collect data (i.e., fuel data, weather data, etc.) that FBAN can use to anticipate the fire movement better. Initially, a fire estimation model is utilized that allows the UAV to use an unscented Kalman filter (UKF) to estimate the fire-front locations and their respective uncertainty. Then a two-part controller is designed for controlling the UAV. The first part of the controller switches between the fire monitoring (FM) mode and the data acquisition (DA) mode. In the fire monitoring mode, the controller determines the most uncertain fire-fronts and calculates target points for the UAV to visit for monitoring the fire evolution. In the data acquisition mode, the controller determines the area ahead of the fire based on the fire movement and calculates virtual target points that the UAV must visit for data acquisition. The second part of the controller includes the motion planning scheme based on the artificial potential field method designed to move the UAV from its current position to the target points provided by the first part, ensuring that all safety considerations (i.e., minimum and maximum flying altitudes) are met. The proposed approach is evaluated in a simulation environment showcasing its ability to monitor the fire and acquire data ahead of the fire.

In the future, we plan to study the possible decentralization of the proposed approach so that a team of UAV agents can collaborate on fire monitoring and data acquisition tasks. Moreover, we plan to investigate adaptive methods for switching between FM and DA modes and virtual target calculation.

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